

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab

ESIL Innovation Summit 2024 Evaluation & Longitudinal Findings

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Introduction

Program Description

The Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab (ESIIL) is a next-generation NSF data synthesis center that enables a global community of environmental data scientists to leverage emerging analytics to develop science-based solutions to pressing environmental challenges. These activities support ESIIL's mission to *"Empower a broad community to accelerate open environmental data science (EDS)"* (www.esiil.org).

This report summarizes the evaluation of the second annual ESIIL Environmental Data Science Innovation Summit, which took place on May 14th – 16th, 2024 in Boulder, CO. The event brought together 151 Earth and Environmental Data Scientists from a variety of disciplines to build and strengthen the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. The Summit theme was "Big Data for Environmental Resilience and Adaptation." It followed an "unconference" meeting format (Budd et al., 2015) that encouraged participant engagement and involvement in shaping the Summit and feedback each day to inform what was included in subsequent days of the meeting. The overarching goals of the 2024 Summit were:

- **Explore big data for environmental resilience and adaptation** by identifying data synthesis opportunities and utilizing ESIIL cloud-computing capabilities.
- **Promote best practices in ethical, open science**, by supporting accessibility and usability of environmental data by all stakeholders. Champion ethical and equitable practices in environmental science, honoring data sovereignty and encouraging the responsible use of AI.
- **Support** environmental data scientists to establish collaborations around data-inspired themes across different disciplines, sectors, career stages, and backgrounds.
- **Encourage the co-production of environmental knowledge** with communities that are experiencing significant environmental challenges.

Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation team used a collaborative approach (King and Stevahn 2013, Shulha et al. 2016) to develop the Summit evaluation activities with the project leadership and used feedback from the first annual Summit to revise evaluation surveys. The week before the Summit, an online Pre-Summit survey was sent to all registered attendees. On the final day of the Summit, attendees were invited to take an online reflection survey to share their experiences at the Summit.

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Executive Summary

Pre-Summit Training Opportunities

80% of reflection survey respondents reported engaging in the Pre-Summit activities. Attending Pre-Summit trainings may have helped respondents achieve their personal goals for the Summit, particularly those with themes of skill development and exploring data science tools and techniques. Of the Pre-Summit activities, respondents reported that the cloud computing and CyVerse Discovery Environment trainings best prepared them for the Summit. To further improve Pre-Summit trainings, respondents recommended providing more guidance and step-by-step instructions in advance, offering different tracks for novices and experts, and providing more opportunities to practice the skills learned.

Snapshot of 2024 Summit Experience and Outcomes

92% Of respondents were very (63%) or moderately (29%) **satisfied overall** with the Summit.

93% Agreed or strongly agreed that they **felt respected** by their colleagues.

92% Agreed or strongly agreed that the Summit **atmosphere** was **relaxed, open, friendly** and **fun**.

78% Agreed or strongly agreed that they learned about **new technologies or techniques** applicable to their research.

76% Of respondents were motivated to **continue to work on EDS** ideas after the Summit to a large or very large extent.

71% Agreed or strongly agreed that the **unconference format worked well**.

Respondents saw a statistically significant **greater overlap between themselves and EDS professionals at the end of the Summit** than before it ($Z = 3.67, p < .05$).

Respondents rated the breakout groups the highest of the Summit activities, noting that they convened enthusiastic collaborators and resulted in effective brainstorming and project planning that could carry on past the Summit. Respondents suggested improvements including more intentionality and time to form and work in the groups, ensuring clarity around the role of the facilitator, and the opportunity to provide feedback about the group goals ahead of time.

Respondents' Takeaways from the Summit

- **Skill Development in Cloud Computing and Data Science:** Gaining skills in cloud computing, GitHub, and managing large datasets to advance work in environmental and data science, navigating complex technological platforms like CyVerse, and applying new methods such as machine learning.
- **Networking and Building Professional Connections:** Forming professional connections from various fields to collaborate with on future projects, teaching, or research.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Problem-Solving:** Collaborating across disciplines allowed attendees to learn from experts in different fields and encouraged innovative problem-solving.
- **Resources and Tools for Research:** Accessing advanced tools, often difficult to do independently, such as CyVerse and cloud computing facilities enhanced research capabilities.
- **New Ideas and Perspectives:** Discussions in breakout groups and presentations led to new research questions or considering applying techniques like AI and big data to existing work.
- **Confidence and Practical Application:** Increased confidence to apply newly learned tools and techniques and practical experience in teamwork, coding, and data analysis, which would influence future projects.
- **Community and Inclusivity:** Respondents left with a sense of belonging and purpose. Many appreciated the open, collaborative atmosphere, which fostered mutual respect and encouraged diverse voices to contribute to discussions.

Comparison of 2023 and 2024 Summit Survey Respondent Demographics

Differences

- There were **202** Summit attendees in **2023** and **151** attendees in **2024**.

Similarities

- Researchers and students represented the largest two role categories held by survey respondents in both 2023 and 2024.
- Survey respondents from 2023 and 2024 Summit evaluations were largely similar in their proportion of U.S. to international home bases and gender.

Respondents' Favorite Parts of the 2024 ESIL Innovation Summit

Key Themes	Highlights
Networking and Community Building	Respondents valued meeting new people, connecting with like-minded individuals, and expanding their professional networks.
Teamwork and Collaboration	Working in small groups and collaborative sessions was highly appreciated for fostering effective teamwork.
Facilitation and Group Dynamics	Many respondents appreciated the guidance provided by facilitators on group dynamics and collaboration.
Learning and Skill Development	Respondents found value in the training sessions, especially those on group science, facilitation, and technical tools.

Key Themes	Highlights
Multiple Perspectives	Many respondents said that the variety of different perspectives represented enriched the Summit experience, specifically highlighting contributions from Indigenous voices.
Engaging Activities and Breakout Sessions	Respondents enjoyed the breakout sessions and hands-on activities.
Presentation and Learning Content	The informative presentations and resources on group and facilitation science were well received.
Organized and Productive	Respondents felt the Summit was well-organized and productive overall.

Respondents' Recommendations for Improving Future Summits

Key Themes	Examples and Recommended Improvements
Time Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration Concerns: Suggestions included extending the Summit to <i>“full three days instead of 2.5”</i> to allow for more relaxation and deeper engagement. • Time Pressure: Many felt overwhelmed by the packed schedule, stating they had <i>“not enough time”</i> during the Summit and reflected that this affected <i>“getting people's creativity going.”</i>
Group Dynamics and Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity of Participants: Observations indicated <i>“fewer non-academic participants present this year,”</i> specifically mentioning the lack of data providers like GBIF and NCAR, and fewer climatologists and geologists. • Team Formation: Respondents suggested that Pre-Summit team-building could help avoid rushed dynamics: <i>“I would have liked to get in teams before the Summit.”</i> • Group Experience: Some groups struggled due to inexperience: <i>“My group was young and didn't have much experience in research or data science.”</i> • Energy Levels: Some respondents noted that <i>“this year's energy felt a little flat,”</i> while recognizing trade-offs with improved productivity.
Facilitation and Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitation Style: Feedback included that facilitators <i>“felt like we were spoken to as children,”</i> indicating a need for a more respectful approach to adult participants. • Expectation Clarity: Many wanted better clarity on the Summit format, with one noting, <i>“It would have helped me to get more of a primer on the structure of the Summit ahead of time.”</i> • Activity Selection: Respondents missed successful past activities like <i>“soap box”</i> and <i>“Rosetta Stone,”</i> suggesting these could enhance engagement and community.
Educational Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training on Tools: Suggestions included <i>“more time to teach the new tools”</i> before diving into group projects, as many were unfamiliar with tools like CyVerse and GitHub.

Key Themes	Examples and Recommended Improvements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills Development: Respondents expressed a desire for a balance between teaching skills and collaboration, proposing <i>“skills tracks in the afternoons”</i> to better integrate learning with group work.
Communication and Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information Sharing: Calls for better pre-Summit communication were prevalent, with one attendee saying, <i>“It seems to have been an intentional choice to let participants struggle,”</i> indicating frustration with the lack of guidance. • Feedback Mechanism: Several suggested implementing continuous feedback throughout the event to adapt and improve.
Content and Topic Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on Topics: Some felt overwhelmed by the breadth of topics, suggesting <i>“fifteen topics is too much”</i> and advocating for a narrower focus for deeper exploration. • Outcome Clarity: Requests included <i>“more examples of possible outcomes for groups”</i> to guide expectations and project work.
Meeting Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitivity in Discussions: Criticism was aimed at the presentation of trauma-related topics, with one participant stating, <i>“The trauma of people of African descent shouldn’t be used in a matter-of-fact manner,”</i> highlighting the need for cultural sensitivity. • Variety in Presentation Topics: Respondents called for including a variety of perspectives in the presentations.
Networking Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Time: Requests for more informal networking opportunities included suggestions for a <i>“general mixer on Thursday evening”</i> to facilitate connections.
Logistics and Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to Tools: Issues arose with infrastructure for collaboration: <i>“It felt that there should have been a plan in place already to facilitate collaboration.”</i> • Organizational Improvements: Suggestions for better organization included improving meal quality and transportation options, as well as hiring an instructional designer for materials.
Format Suggestions for Future Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longer Summit Format: Proposals for extending the event duration included <i>“making it a week long”</i> or adding <i>“extra time to work in the clouds”</i> to enhance hands-on experience. • Separate Meetings: Recommendations to hold separate meetings focused on learning tools versus collaborative research to avoid overwhelming participants were noted. • Facilitation of Outcomes: Ideas included creating mechanisms to support ongoing collaboration post-Summit, with suggestions for <i>“providing some incentive for the working groups to continue.”</i>

¹ Icons in the Executive Summary provided by the Noun Project’s creators: Iconathon, Imam, Izwar Muis, Sitaesmi, Studio 365, Robert Chiaver, Thomas Le Bas, and Zuri.

Summit Attendee Characteristics

Summit and Survey Participation

There were 151 attendees at the 2024 ESIL Innovation Summit. Fifty-two attendees responded to the Summit pre-survey (34% response rate) and 62 responded to the Summit reflection survey (41% response rate). The Summit served an international audience with 90% of respondents reporting that they live in the U.S. and 10% reporting that they live outside of the U.S. Survey respondents were from 19 U.S. States and five other countries: Germany, Canada, Norway, Panama, and Sweden (Figure 1).

Figure 1
Heat map of 2024 Summit survey respondents

Note. Red areas represent a higher concentration of survey respondents.

Respondent Demographic Information

Demographic data in this report were collected in May 2024, following NSF guidelines for demographic data collection at that time.

Fifty-two percent of survey respondents identified as women, and most others (44%) identified as men. Four percent of respondents chose another response or preferred not to answer (Table 1).

Table 1

Survey Respondent Gender	
52%	Women
44%	Men
4%	Another Response

The majority of respondents identified as White, Caucasian, European, or European American (56%). Respondents also identified as Asian or Asian American (17%); Black, African American, or African (15%); American Indian or Alaska Native (6%); or Hispanic, Latinx, or Hispanic or Latinx American (6%). Six percent of respondents preferred not to answer, 6% selected more than one category, and 2% included a written response describing their race or ethnicity (Table 2).

Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation

Just over half of respondents (52%) had earned a **Doctoral degree**, 35% held **Master’s degrees**, and 6% had completed some graduate work. Two percent of respondents had earned a Bachelor’s degree, 2% had earned an Associate degree, and 2% preferred not to answer (Table 3).

Field of Study: Survey respondents were also asked to indicate the field in which they received their highest degree. These degrees encompassed a **range of academic disciplines**, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of Environmental Data Science (EDS), with individuals from a wide array of fields contributing to its advancement and application (Table 4).

Table 2

Survey Respondent Race and Ethnicity	
56%	White, Caucasian, European, or European American
17%	Asian or Asian American
15%	Black, African American, or African
6%	American Indian or Alaska Native
6%	Hispanic, Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
6%	I prefer not to answer
0%	Middle Eastern or North African; Middle Eastern or North African American
2%	Not listed (<i>please specify</i>)
6%	More than one selection

Note. “More than one selection” and “Not listed” are not included in the total percentage because they both include multiple responses selected.

Table 3

Survey Respondents’ Highest Level of Education	
52%	Doctoral degree
35%	Master’s degree
6%	Some graduate work
2%	Bachelor’s degree
2%	Associate degree
2%	I prefer not to answer

Table 4

Natural Sciences	Engineering and Applied Sciences	Social Sciences and Humanities	Interdisciplinary & Miscellaneous
Atmospheric Science	Aeronautics/ Astronautics Engineering	Anthropology	Public Health
Biogeochemistry	Applied Mathematics	Communication Studies	Statistics
Biology	Biomedical Science	Crisis Informatics	Theoretical Physics
Botany	Biotechnology	Education	
Earth System Science	Computer Science	Environmental Data Science	
Ecology	Geological Engineering	Environmental Management	
Environmental Science	Operations Research	Lakota Studies	
Environmental Toxicology		Law	
Geology		Library Science	
Hydrology		Policy and Management	
Marine Science		Science Management	
Marine Biology		Sociology	
Physics			
Plant Breeding and Genetics			
Soil Science			
Wildlife and Conservation Biology			

Career Stage: Twenty-three percent of respondents were **students**, and just over a third of respondents (35%) described themselves as **Early Career** (0 – 5 years of professional experience or post-doctoral fellow). Thirteen percent were **Mid-Career** (6 – 15 years of professional experience). Another 23% were at a **Senior** stage in their career (more than 15 years of experience), and 6% reported “Other” (Figure 2).

Figure 2

Affiliation: Almost three-fourths of respondents work at an **Academic (higher education) institution (73%)**, followed by Non-profit: Research and Development (FFRDC/National Labs/etc.) organizations (12%), Tribal organizations (6%), other non-profit organizations (6%), Federal Government agencies (4%) and Self-employed (4%). Four percent of respondents chose “Other” and reported being in retirement or employment with international organizations.

Academic Affiliations Represented. Of those respondents working at academic institutions, the majority reported affiliation with a **Research-Intensive institution (69%)**. Eighteen percent of academic affiliations included institutions serving both undergraduate and graduate students, 8% served primarily undergraduates, and 3% included a community college. Some respondents also reported affiliation with a minority-serving institution (5%); a Hispanic-serving institution (5%); or a tribal college or university (8%) (Table 5).

Table 5

69%	Research Intensive
18%	Undergraduate & Graduate student serving
8%	Primarily Undergraduate student serving
5%	Hispanic-Serving Institution
8%	Tribal College or University
5%	Minority-Serving Institution
3%	Community College/ 2-yr College

Note. The sum of percentages exceeds 100% because respondents could select more than one response.

Non-Academic Affiliations. Respondents who do not work for an academic institution described the main organization they are affiliated with, which were grouped in four different non-academic affiliations (Table 6):

Table 6

Government Agencies, Labs, and Contractors	Non-Profit and NGO Sector	Research and Education Sector	Private Sector
Department of Energy user facilities	American Indian organizations	Institutions for applied science on conservation	Consultancy companies
Earth & space science agencies	Consortium of Tribal Colleges and Universities	Institutions funded by NSF	Geospatial data providers
Federal land-management agencies	Environmental non-profits	National observatories	Publicly traded, for-profit companies
Federal research agencies	NGOs funded through NSF	Research teams of environmental non-profits	
Federally funded research and development centers	Non-profit observatories/lab operations and management		
Government contractors	Organizations improving data resources		
National laboratories			

Primary role in the Environmental Data Science (EDS) Field: Survey respondents were asked to choose their primary roles in the broad field of EDS. **Researchers (35%) represented the largest group at the Summit** with smaller percentages of people who primarily identified as a Student (19%), Educator (12%), Technician (8%), Director or Program Manager (8%), or Analyst (4%). Two percent of respondents preferred not to answer, and 13% selected “Other” (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Note. Other roles specified by respondents included DEI Lead, Officer, Team Science Expert, Tribal Advisor/Contractor, and Project Planning and Development.

Disciplinary fields in EDS: The most commonly selected EDS fields selected by respondents included **Environmental Science (56%), Computer/Data Science (33%), Biological Science (33%), Geoscience (27%), and Artificial Intelligence (23%)**. Fewer respondents represented Social Sciences (15%), Math (6%), Chemistry/ Biochemistry (6%), Engineering (2%) and Economics (3%). The majority of respondents selected more than one response as their main field in EDS. Open-ended “Other” responses (19%) included: DEIA, Ecology, Law, Genetics, Natural Hazards, Communications, Climate Justice, Indigenous Studies, and Fire Science.

Professional Society Memberships: The list of memberships comprises a **wide range of professional societies**, including those related to natural sciences, social sciences, mathematics, ecology, geophysics, biology, geography, and more. Some societies are discipline-specific (e.g., American Mathematical Society, Ecological Society of America), while others are more broadly focused on fields like geophysics, earth sciences, and data

science. Additionally, there are some societies dedicated to supporting underrepresented groups (e.g., American Indian Science and Engineering Society, SACNAS) and promoting diversity in STEM. Several societies (e.g., American Geophysical Union and the Ecological Society of America) appeared multiple times in the list, indicating their prominence and potential popularity among professionals.

Accommodation Requests

The pre-survey asked respondents to describe any accommodation needs. Nine attendees provided responses to this question. Below is a summary of themes and representative verbatim quotes.

Accessibility for Hearing Impairments:

- *"Captions"*
- *"T-coil for assistive hearing would be great for any big-room events."*

Physical Accessibility and Mobility Needs:

- *"I am recovering from a knee surgery and may need to prop my leg up."*
- *"Frequent breaks for bathroom / stretches (for pregnancy)."*

Visual Accessibility:

- *"Larger font sizes on presentations, please!"*

Mental Health and Sensory Needs:

- *"Mental health: I leave when I need to...."*
- *"low/reduced sensory spaces"*

Dietary Accommodations:

- *"high-protein low-carb vegan food"*
- *"Vegan food for in-person events"*

General Clear Communication:

- *"Explain things clearly"*

Pre-Summit Participation and Summit Goals

Participation in Pre-Summit Activities

Prior to the Summit, the leadership team engaged Summit attendees in optional Pre-Summit training sessions. Topics included basics of cloud computing, collaborating with other people, team science, and cultural intelligence.

80% of Summit reflection survey respondents reported engaging in the Pre-Summit activities, with:

- **72%** participating in Head in the Clouds: Navigating the Basics of Cloud Computing (April 24, 2024)
- **69%** participating in Feet on the Ground: Collaborating with Other People Using Cloud Computing (May 1, 2024)
- **58%** participating in Voices in Concert: Cultural Intelligence, the Art of Team Science, and Community Skills (May 6, 2024)

On the Summit reflection survey, respondents were also asked to rate how useful each training was and how well the technical trainings prepared them for the Summit. Across the board, most respondents who attended a given training agreed or strongly agreed that the event helped prepare them for the Summit. Of these, respondents tended to agree or strongly agree most frequently that the CyVerse Discovery Environment and the Cloud Computing trainings helped prepare for the Summit (Figure 4).

Figure 4

Note. Respondents who did not attend a given training selected N/A.

Respondents' Personal Summit Goals

The Summit pre-survey asked respondents to share 1-3 personal goals for the Summit. Common themes in their responses are summarized below.

- **Networking and Collaboration:** The most common theme among respondents was the desire to network, connect, and collaborate with others. Many responses specifically mentioned the goal of building professional networks, meeting like-minded individuals, connecting with researchers and data scientists, and establishing collaborations that could lead to future projects. Some respondents also expressed an interest in forming or joining working groups that extend beyond the Summit.
- **Learning and Skill Development:** Respondents were eager to learn new skills, especially in areas such as data science, cloud computing, coding, and data management. The Summit was seen as an opportunity to gain knowledge in big data, earth data science, statistical analysis, and environmental data science applications. There was a particular emphasis on learning how to apply these skills practically in research or classroom settings.
- **Exploring Data Science Tools and Techniques:** Many respondents were interested in understanding the latest tools, techniques, and methodologies in environmental data science (EDS). This included learning about data sources, data analysis methods, reproducibility, cloud data management, and new applications of these technologies in environmental research. Respondents also expressed a desire to explore how these tools can enhance their own work or contribute to teaching.
- **Focus on Environmental Resilience and Sustainability:** A number of respondents were motivated by a broader mission to address environmental challenges through data science. Goals included exploring research questions related to resilience, understanding how data science can contribute to environmental sustainability, and identifying ways to engage in impactful projects that support these aims.
- **Accessibility and Community Engagement:** Several respondents emphasized the importance of making environmental data broadly accessible. Some mentioned a focus on a welcoming meeting culture and learning about best practices in data science ethics.
- **Specific Career and Academic Goals:** Responses also included personal career ambitions, such as finding potential PhD advisors, future employers, or expanding professional networks to support specific career paths in biodiversity, resilience work, or academia. Some respondents were interested in integrating what they learned into their teaching or bringing new insights back to their home institutions.
- **Interest in ESILL's Approach and Activities:** Several responses highlighted a specific interest in understanding ESILL's approach to collaborative data science, its Innovation Summit format, and how these can be leveraged for future collaborations or adapted in other contexts.

Respondents' Recommendation for Improving Pre-Summit Trainings

Themes that arose from respondents' recommendations for improving the Pre-Summit trainings and exemplary quotes are provided below.

Adjust the Pacing and Structure of Trainings

- Respondents recommended breaking sessions into smaller, more manageable chunks and providing step-by-step directions in advance.
 - *"The pacing of the first session could have been improved. It was initially too fast, and as a result was slowed way down, which was then too slow."*
- Consider offering separate tracks for different skill levels.
 - *"They should be split between novices and experts."*

Provide Pre-Recorded Videos and Step-by-Step Guides

- Provide recorded videos and instructional content in advance.
 - *"Offer more basic/introductory data science lessons/experiences."*
 - *"Optional training or video resources should be considered."*
- Include links shared during live sessions in video descriptions.

Enhance Technical Onboarding and Collaboration Training

- Simplify the technical onboarding (particularly with tools like Git/GitHub and CyVerse) with a slower, more guided approach, and focus on asynchronous, rather than real-time, collaboration.
- Provide practical examples and hands-on exercises for collaboration, especially focusing on common challenges like permissions and repository management.
 - *"Permissions were an issue I think, so repo clones were made and then multiple versions were being worked on separately."*

Increase Clarity and Context of Sessions

- Offer a conceptual overview of each session and ensure consistency.
 - *"It would help to more formally explain the conceptual landscape/overview... What part of this big-picture agenda does this small part we've just run or set-up take care of?"*
 - *"...Inconsistency of terminology... made it very hard to follow."*
- Share agendas, expectations, and technical requirements ahead of time.
 - *"Prepare handouts in advance with clear steps to follow."*
 - *"Sharing to-do list[s] before the event date would help participants to have an idea about what to expect."*

Increase Time for Practice and Group Interaction

- Extend the duration of pre-Summit activities to allow for more in-depth training and group discussions.
- Incorporate more practice sessions for coding and collaborative work.
 - *"It would be great if we could have some practice sessions to let people feel more comfortable on coding."*

Summit Evaluation Outcomes

Participant Satisfaction with the ESIL Innovation Summit

Ninety-two percent of respondents were very or moderately **satisfied** with the ESIL Innovation Summit overall (63% “Very Satisfied;” 29% “Moderately Satisfied”).

Respondents generally agreed that the various components of the Summit agenda were effective. Respondents rated **breakout group time** the most highly, with **87%** agreeing or strongly agreeing that this was an effective part of the Summit (Figure 5).

Figure 5

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following parts of the ESIL Innovator Summit were effective? (N = 62)

Evaluation of Breakout Group Work

A majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that breakout groups gathered **enthusiastic collaborators (83%)**, **brainstorming was effective (81%)**, groups were able to **develop project plans (75%)** and **outlines (72%)**, groups developed plans to **collaborate beyond the Summit (65%)**, and that **collaboration seemed feasible (58%)** (Figure 6).

Figure 6

Additional Feedback on Breakout Groups

Clarify Facilitator Roles

Several respondents noted that they were unclear about the facilitators' roles, leading to confusion in group dynamics.

- *“Ask facilitators to explain their role (ours was note taking only and I didn’t know that until the last day).”*

Group Formation and Structure

Many respondents felt that group formation was rushed or arbitrary, impacting the cohesion and outcomes of the groups.

- *“Formation of breakout groups was something of a lottery... have stickers/identifiers that participants can use to show their expertise/affinities for a more organic process.”*

Time Constraints

A common theme was the need for more time, both for forming groups and for achieving meaningful outcomes in discussions and projects.

- *“Too little time to choose our groups... more time to talk to people and figure out where we belong.”*

- *“We started becoming more integrated at the very end, I just wish we had more time together.”*

Broad Expertise and Participation

Some respondents appreciated the variety of expertise in the groups, while others felt that certain voices dominated or that the groups could have been better balanced.

- *“The loudest voice was the vote, and the elder’s opinion was taken, whereas the younger ones that had ideas were not heard.”*

Facilitator Impact on Group Success

The role of the facilitator was noted as a key reason for group success when well-managed, especially in creating a welcoming and democratic space.

- *“The facilitator of our group is a huge reason I feel our group was a success... because of his ability to guide the group in an inclusive and democratic manner.”*

Tech Support and Event Organization

Respondents praised the overall organization of the event and the effectiveness of tech support.

- *“Tech support was fantastic—I never felt looked down upon for needing help.”*
- *“Well organized and well run :)”*

Suggestions for Improvement

Respondents offered several constructive suggestions, including better transparency in setting goals, iterative feedback, and allowing flexibility for switching groups.

- *“More transparency in how the initial questions were generated and what the expected outcomes are would be great... send topics out ahead and ask for public comment.”*

Evaluation of Technical Support and Cyberinfrastructure

Roughly three-quarters of respondents agreed that they learned about **new technologies or techniques applicable to their research (78%)**, **gained an understanding of data science (74%)** and **cyberinfrastructure (72%)**, and learned about new **opportunities for synthesis of data in their field (71%)** (Figure 7).

Figure 7

Evaluation of the Unconference Format

The Summit was designed following the common elements of an “unconference” style meeting (Budd et al., 2015). Survey items and observations of the Summit conducted by three evaluators focused on the following six broad design elements of an unconference style meeting:

- There are opportunities for participants to directly influence what is happening at the Summit (e.g., through topics, presentations, sharing of interest and expertise).
- The discussions and engagement in the breakout groups appear relevant for attendees.
- There is an emphasis on contributions from every participant and facilitation is welcoming regardless of how experienced they are (“no idea is too trivial”).
- The Summit atmosphere is relaxed, open, friendly, fun, and welcoming (e.g., for newcomers and those new to EDS).
- Participants learn about useful skills or tools related to EDS, or they applied skills and tools to EDS work.
- There are opportunities for and encouragement of collaborative work and interactive knowledge exchange/transdisciplinary work.

Reflection survey respondents provided feedback on the unconference style format (Figure 8). Highlights included:

Welcoming Atmosphere: Most survey respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the **atmosphere was relaxed and friendly (92%)** and that the Summit **welcomed contributions and ideas from all participants, regardless of background experience (87%)**.

Collaboration and Networking: Most respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the Summit offered adequate **opportunities for collaborative, transdisciplinary work and exchange of ideas (87%), networking (87%), relevant breakout group activities (86%),** and was **welcoming for newcomers to the field (84%).**

Participant Influence: The majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that there were opportunities to **directly influence what was happening each day at the Summit (68%).**

Application of Skills or Tools: Over three-fourths of respondents agreed that they had **learned about and/or applied useful skills or tools related to EDS at the Summit (78%).**

Figure 8

Most respondents also tended to agree or strongly agree that **speakers and presenters were engaging (82%)**, the Summit facilitated **networking opportunities (77%)**, the **online resources were useful (76%)**, goals were **well-communicated (73%)**, and the overall **unconference format worked well (71%)** (Figure 9).

Figure 9

Participants' Perspectives on Being EDS Professionals

Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted to evaluate changes in respondents' pre-survey and reflection survey responses about how they identify with being a member of the EDS community. Before and after the Summit, respondents were asked to choose the picture that best described the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of an Environmental Data Science (EDS) professional. Results showed a significant change such **that respondents saw a greater overlap between themselves and EDS professionals at the end of the Summit** compared to before the Summit ($Z = 3.67, p < .05$), (Figure 10).

Figure 10

Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Respondents were also asked to rate the extent to which they agreed with statements about their sense of belonging in the EDS community. Respondents' agreement did not significantly change from pre- to post-survey for "I belong to the EDS Community" ($Z = 1.86, p = .062$) and "Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity" ($Z = 1.95, p = .05$) (Figure 11).

Figure 11

ESIIL Culture

The majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the **contributions of all group members were valued (91%)**. Respondents also agreed or strongly agreed that they **felt comfortable providing feedback (85%)** and **contributing opposing viewpoints (86%)** (Figures 12 and 13).

Figure 12

Figure 13

Summit Overall Highlights

The best parts of the ESIL Innovation Summit, according to respondents, can be summarized into the following key themes:

- **Networking and Community Building:** Respondents valued meeting new people, connecting with like-minded individuals, and expanding their professional networks.
- **Teamwork and Collaboration:** Working in small groups and collaborative sessions was highly appreciated for fostering effective teamwork.
- **Facilitation and Group Dynamics:** Many respondents appreciated the guidance provided by facilitators on group dynamics and collaboration.
- **Learning and Skill Development:** Respondents found value in the training sessions, especially those on group science, facilitation, and technical tools.
- **Multiple Perspectives:** Many respondents said that the range of different perspectives represented enriched the Summit experience, specifically highlighting contributions from Indigenous participants.
- **Engaging Activities and Breakout Sessions:** Respondents enjoyed the breakout sessions and hands-on activities.
- **Presentation and Learning Content:** The informative presentations and resources on group and facilitation science were well received.
- **Positive Feedback:** Respondents felt the Summit was well-organized and productive overall.

Areas for Improvement

Survey respondents recommended the following improvements for future Summits:

Time Management

- **Duration Concerns:** Suggestions included extending the Summit to *“full three days instead of 2.5”* to allow for more relaxation and deeper engagement.
- **Time Pressure:** Many felt overwhelmed by the packed schedule, stating they had *“not enough time”* during the Summit and reflected that this affected *“getting people’s creativity going.”*

Group Dynamics and Participation

- **Broadening Perspectives:** Observations indicated *“fewer non-academic participants present this year,”* specifically mentioning the lack of data providers like GBIF and NCAR, and fewer climatologists and geologists.
- **Team Formation:** Respondents suggested that Pre-Summit team-building could help avoid rushed dynamics: *“I would have liked to get in teams before the Summit.”*
- **Group Experience:** Some groups struggled due to inexperience: *“My group was young and didn’t have much experience in research or data science.”*
- **Energy Levels:** Some respondents noted that *“this year’s energy felt a little flat,”* while recognizing trade-offs with improved productivity.

Facilitation and Structure

- **Facilitation Style:** Feedback included that facilitators *“felt like we were spoken to as children,”* indicating a need for a more respectful approach to adult participants.

- **Expectation Clarity:** Many wanted better clarity on the Summit format, with one noting, *“It would have helped me to get more of a primer on the structure of the Summit ahead of time.”*
- **Activity Selection:** Respondents missed successful past activities like *“soap box”* and *“Rosetta Stone,”* suggesting these could enhance engagement and community.

Educational Needs

- **Training on Tools:** Suggestions included *“more time to teach the new tools”* before diving into group projects, as many were unfamiliar with tools like CyVerse and GitHub.
- **Skills Development:** Respondents expressed a desire for a balance between teaching skills and collaboration, proposing *“skills tracks in the afternoons”* to better integrate learning with group work.

Communication and Transparency

- **Information Sharing:** Calls for better pre-Summit communication were prevalent, with one attendee saying, *“It seems to have been an intentional choice to let participants struggle,”* indicating frustration with the lack of guidance.
- **Feedback Mechanism:** Several suggested implementing continuous feedback throughout the event to adapt and improve.

Content and Topic Management

- **Focus on Topics:** Some felt overwhelmed by the breadth of topics, suggesting *“fifteen topics is too much”* and advocating for a narrower focus for deeper exploration.
- **Outcome Clarity:** Requests included *“more examples of possible outcomes for groups”* to guide expectations and project work.

Meeting Culture

- **Sensitivity in Discussions:** Criticism was aimed at the presentation of trauma-related topics, with one participant stating, *“The trauma of people of African descent shouldn’t be used in a matter-of-fact manner,”* highlighting the need for cultural sensitivity.
- **Variety in Presentation Topics:** Respondents called for including a variety of perspectives in the presentations.

Networking Opportunities

- **Social Time:** Requests for more informal networking opportunities included suggestions for a *“general mixer on Thursday evening”* to facilitate connections.

Logistics and Infrastructure

- **Access to Tools:** Issues arose with infrastructure for collaboration: *“It felt that there should have been a plan in place already to facilitate collaboration.”*
- **Organizational Improvements:** Suggestions for better organization included improving meal quality and transportation options, as well as hiring an instructional designer for materials.

Format Suggestions for Future Events

- **Longer Summit Format:** Proposals for extending the event duration included *“making it a week long”* or adding *“extra time to work in the clouds”* to enhance hands-on experience.
- **Separate Meetings:** Recommendations to hold separate meetings focused on learning tools versus collaborative research to avoid overwhelming participants were noted.
- **Facilitation of Outcomes:** Ideas included creating mechanisms to support ongoing collaboration post-Summit, with suggestions for *“providing some incentive for the working groups to continue.”*

In a final open-ended question, respondents were asked to *Please share any other feedback you have about the ESILL Innovation Summit*. Themes and representative verbatim responses are included below. These themes were further categorized as Positive Feedback, indicating aspects of the Summit that participants appreciated or enjoyed and Areas for Improvement, indicating suggestions made to improve the Summit.

Positive Feedback

Overall Experience

- *“Great job facilitating team and the organizers!”*
- *“Thank you Thank you Thank you. This entire Summit was well executed - from the application process, registration, food (I was well fed), session facilitators, ice breakers, breakout group selection - everything was well planned and executed fantastically. Thank you for keeping to timeframes and moving forward. This was an amazing experience!”*
- *“I greatly appreciate the inclusive nature of the EDS conference, and the efforts that were made to make everyone feel welcome and comfortable.”*
- *“Good job! I really appreciated the effort by the organizers. I felt heard in that improvements I wanted to see after the first year were implemented.”*
- *“The exceptionally brilliant implementation of the Summit shows how intentional and thoughtful the organizers were! Amazing job!”*
- *“Thanks for a great Summit! I think you guys are breaking way on a new type of exciting and useful conference here.”*

Learning and Collaboration

- *“The Summit was a great opportunity to learn, collaborate, and present how one can bring their knowledge to the table, to be helpful and respected.”*
- *“I feel that the Summit has helped me understand what it takes to be part of a community that helps each other and makes one another grow as a person in and out of the work environment.”*
- *“Nothing else to add. This was an incredible experience and I’ll most definitely be applying again next year.”*
- *“Thank you so much for the opportunity to participate! I enjoyed it very much!”*
- *“Keep on the good work!”*

Suggestions for Future Events

- *“I would love to attend an in-person workshop dedicated specifically to cyverse so that I can engage in guided exploration of its potential and learn how to utilize this infrastructure.”*
- *“It would be cool to share tools we use, how we can consolidate documentation and file formats to make tooling and data easily accessible in earth science.”*

Areas for Improvement

Meeting Culture

- *“Maybe inviting some teams from some of the more under-represented groups at the Summit would help them feel less of a ‘one and only’.”*
- *“There weren’t enough non-biologists this year! I didn’t meet that many folks from other disciplines, at least. Also, it would be great to include more private and public employees from relevant organizations to get truly diverse insights regarding implementation.”*

Session Content and Facilitation

- *“The facilitators were really lovely, but there seemed to be little room for failure or conflict. It’s hard to be truly innovative if the sticky grey areas are entirely ignored or dismissed.”*
- *“The talk about AI was really inaccessible... as a non-data scientist, it was just a bit beyond my ability to really appreciate.”*
- *“Maybe have some sessions planned to educate the basics of cloud Infrastructure and how it can be powerful in facilitating data intensive science.”*

Expectations and Specific Concerns

- *“My feedback has been somewhat negative because I had extremely high expectations for this event that were not met in some cases.”*
- *“It was not the appropriate place to discuss Black legacy topics and issues. I also didn’t leave trained in the technology that I thought I would be.”*
- *“I’m quite interested in the future of ESIL and how it supports what these new breakout groups do. I hope to see more partnerships developed.”*

General Suggestions for Improvement

- *“Increase the Summit time would be good.”*
- *“Encourage more people to attend the leadership session before the Summit. Learnt a lot.”*
- *“I think there is still work to be done but I know developing new kinds of relating is hard and takes time and iteration.”*

Summit Outcomes: Overall Impacts and Innovation

A subset of open-ended questions was asked only of the ESIL leadership team, Advisory board members, and Summit breakout group leaders. There was only 1 respondent who elected to answer these questions. The responses are given verbatim below:

Impacts of the ESIL Innovation Summit Over the Next 6 Months

“Some of the groups that formed will continue to work together and build momentum, potentially turning their ideas into working groups or publications. I think many people will also leverage some of the connections they built at the Summit.”

Impacts of the ESIL Innovation Summit on Innovation

“Bringing together people with diverse ideas and backgrounds to work together on a topic may lead to some breakthroughs or ideas that wouldn't have happened otherwise.”

Impacts of the ESIL Innovation Summit on a Decadal EDS Research Agenda

Note: no survey respondents elected to answer this question.

Impacts of the Summit Toward Advancing the field of EDS

Several themes emerged regarding how the ESIL Innovation Summit advanced the field of EDS.

Representative verbatim responses are included below each theme (N = 66).

Collaboration Across Disciplines and Expertise: Bringing together people from different backgrounds and disciplines to work on shared challenges was a key element.

- *"Bringing diverse expertise, career levels, cultural differences, and education levels into one place to collaborate and understand and learn from each other."*
- *"Bringing people together who would not otherwise have interacted, from diverse institutions/organizations/career types."*

Creating a Welcoming Environment: The welcoming atmosphere helped participants share ideas and knowledge without fear, fostering a positive learning environment.

- *"Facilitating a welcoming environment to share the knowledge without a fear greatly helped to advance the EDS."*
- *"What stood out to me the most was the welcoming theme... teaching them how to work together, and fostering an ethos of respect and cocreation."*

Training and Learning Opportunities: Respondents appreciated the hands-on training and resources, which helped them learn new tools and methods to advance their work.

- *"Teaching participants how to manage data in GitHub. Encouraging participants to explore digital data sets."*
- *"Training participants to set up and use Cyverse, GitHub, and scripts."*

Networking and Building Connections: Networking and the formation of new collaborations across fields and career stages were emphasized as valuable outcomes of the Summit.

- *"Provides a powerful model of innovative problem-solving by bringing together people from different backgrounds and skills."*
- *"I think the diverse backgrounds of the participants were very useful. It wasn't just environmental scientists/ecologists, but also sociologists, public health officials, data scientists, etc."*

Advancing Interdisciplinary and Collaborative Research: The Summit enabled participants to advance research by working together on interdisciplinary projects, often using modern tools and techniques.

- *"Fostered cross-pollination among people unlikely to meet other ways. Seeded ideas of team science and productive interdisciplinary collaboration."*
- *"It brought together motivated, experienced people who were excited to collaborate with people of all backgrounds and consider novel approaches to the topics."*

Utilization of Advanced Tools and Cyberinfrastructure: The Summit provided access to cutting-edge tools like cloud computing and AI, which empowered participants to further their research.

- *"Providing cyberinfrastructure that is usually not easily accessible to all also gave a great push to advance EDS."*
- *"Teaching people about how to use cloud computing in their own work, at all kinds of levels."*

Long-Term Impact and Future Innovation: Respondents believed that while immediate effects might be limited, the Summit laid the groundwork for long-term innovation and collaboration.

- *"I think this conference is the type that doesn't have a huge immediate effect, but the effects will continue to grow and be seen down the line."*
- *"Likely a few of the groups will develop their ideas further to create an innovative tool or working group that will benefit the community."*

Survey Respondents' Takeaways from the Summit

Summit attendees were asked to describe three takeaways they gained from the ESIIIL Innovation Summit. Below are common themes identified among their responses (N = 69):

- **Skill Development in Cloud Computing and Data Science:** Respondents frequently highlighted gaining skills in cloud computing, GitHub, and managing large datasets. These skills were essential for advancing their work in environmental and data science, helping them navigate complex technological platforms like CyVerse and apply new methods such as machine learning.
- **Networking and Building Professional Connections:** A key theme was the formation of valuable professional networks and contacts. Many respondents mentioned connecting with colleagues and experts from various fields, which they plan to collaborate with on future projects, teaching, or research.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Problem-Solving:** The Summit fostered collaboration across disciplines, allowing respondents to learn from experts in different fields. This approach encouraged innovative problem-solving, with attendees exchanging ideas and working on interdisciplinary approaches to environmental data science challenges.
- **Resources and Tools for Research:** Many respondents appreciated access to advanced tools, such as CyVerse and cloud computing facilities, that enhanced their research capabilities. These resources, often difficult to access independently, were seen as pivotal in advancing respondents' research projects.
- **New Ideas and Perspectives:** The Summit inspired fresh ideas and broadened respondents' perspectives on environmental data science and related fields. Discussions in breakout groups and presentations led many to develop new research questions or consider applying techniques like AI and big data to their work.
- **Confidence and Practical Application:** Several respondents reported feeling more confident in their ability to apply newly learned tools and techniques in their work. They also noted gaining practical experience in teamwork, coding, and data analysis, which would directly influence their future projects.
- **Community building:** The event emphasized community building, which left respondents with a sense of belonging and purpose. Many appreciated the open, collaborative atmosphere, which fostered mutual respect and encouraged many voices to contribute to discussions.

Figure 14

Seventy-six percent of respondents indicated that they were **motivated to continue to work and innovate on ideas related to EDS** after the Summit to a very large or large extent (Figure 14).

Reflections on the 2024 ESIL Innovation Summit: Longitudinal Survey Results

Approximately 10 months after the 2024 ESIL Innovation Summit, 144 participants were emailed a longitudinal reflection survey, excluding those who opted out of future surveys about the 2024 Summit. 7 emails were also returned as undeliverable at the address on file. In total, the survey went out to 137 participants. 30 out of 137 people responded to the survey (a 22% response rate). Responses to the longitudinal survey are summarized in the section below.

Personal Benefit

👍👍👍 100% of respondents
✅👍👍 agreed that the ESIL

Innovation Summit was beneficial for them, with 57% strongly agreeing (Figure 15).

Figure 15

Application of Concepts, Skills, and Tools

Participants were asked, *how have you applied concepts, skills, tools, or resources that you learned about at the 2023 Summit, if at all? Please elaborate.* Table 7 describes common themes from their open-ended responses (total responses $N = 23$).

Table 7

Key Themes	Highlights
Technical Tools & Skills	Respondents noted using GitHub and R for education, collaboration, and improved data sharing practices, CyVerse for storing and sharing data, shifting from downloading data to streaming and cloud computing approaches, using Jupyter Notebooks and Quarto documents for reproducibility & documentation, and improved awareness and use of platforms like NEON.
Collaboration & Networking	Summit connections led to the formation of new collaborations and proposal submissions. Several respondents are active members of working groups, including those focused on Indigenous data sovereignty and climate monitoring.
Research Methods	Respondents mentioned applying various research methods, including bioacoustics analyses, Indigenous-led data labeling, and private landowner management. Additionally, respondents have used summit-inspired resources to plan future research and enhance current research frameworks.
Community-Centered Data Practices	Respondents reported an increase in attention to reusability and accessibility of code and software in general, a consideration of user needs before tool development, and attention to data ethics, data property, and community-centered practices.
Professional & Soft Skills	Respondents gained team building, interpersonal, and meeting facilitation skills, and an increased comfort and effectiveness in scientific communication, especially in collaborative and cross-disciplinary settings. Some expressed interest in leadership development as well.

The Advancement of the Field of EDS

Participants were asked, *In which ways, if at all, do you think the ESIIIL Innovation Summit has advanced the field of Environmental Data Science?* Table 8 describes common themes from their open-ended responses (total responses $N = 25$).

Table 8

Key Themes	Highlights
Interdisciplinary Collaboration & Networking	Respondents widely praised the Summit for bringing together diverse individuals across disciplines, career stages, and backgrounds, and fostering new partnerships and team formations that wouldn't have occurred otherwise.
Innovation & Idea Generation	Respondents noted the event sparked creative thinking and generated novel research directions, and it encouraged brainstorming across varied expertise areas.
Welcoming Atmosphere	Respondents felt the event provided a welcoming space for newcomers to the field, creating a stronger, more interconnected community and centered underrepresented voices.
Cloud Computing Advancements	Respondents said the event supported transition to cloud-based workflows, enabling easier data sharing, integration, and storage across teams & promoted scalable solutions for analyzing large environmental datasets.
Access to Tools & Data Infrastructure	Respondents were introduced to platforms like Cyverse and cloud computing tools. Additionally, respondents said the event lowered technical barriers, making data science more accessible to non-coders and broader audiences.

Continuing Work from the Summit

46% of respondents have **continued working on ideas** generated at the Summit (Figure 16).

In an open-ended question, respondents were invited to elaborate on the previous question. 12 respondents include comments. Their verbatim responses are listed below:

- *We submitted a proposal for a working group using a project idea that we generated during the summit*
- *Well my group submitted our proposal. Just waiting to hear back on that.*
- *I've dropped and picked up the project my working group started multiple times. The rest of the team was uninterested, but I likely will finish it at some point.*
- *Our team put together a proposal for a working group surrounding a project on the resilience of plant-pollinator interactions in the face of global change. Our team has since used several tools available to us through ESIL as well as the greater ESIL network.*
- *I have been inspired by *Maka Sitomniya: Preserving Mother Earth by Asserting Lakota Sovereignty in Earth Data Science*. The *Maka Sitomniya* initiative focuses on Indigenous sovereignty in Earth Data Science, ensuring that Indigenous communities control, manage, and interpret their environmental data. [Evaluator Note: The respondent went on to describe integrating Indigenous data sovereignty principles into their own work since participating in the 2024 Summit. The exact response for this description is not included to keep the respondent's identity confidential.]*
- *Currently a member of a working group. We have met in person and regularly on Zoom to work on or ideas.*
- *I did come to the first summit with a project of building a climate platform but coming to the summit helped me refine many types of work flows.*
- *Collaboration on data science projects with ESIL personnel.*
- *I am modelling floodplains in the Amazon, and the Summit helped me searching for alternative ways of processing my data and finding new data.*
- *I have been part of a working group (Macrophenology). We continuously talk about data sharing through Cyverse and other aspects of collaboration which closely aligns with learning from the summit.*

Figure 16

Engagement with the Community Post-Event

 79% of respondents are receiving communications through the **ESIL network email listserv**, **54%** of respondents created an **account with Cyverse**, and **54%** of respondents continued working with **professional connections made at the Summit** (Figure 17).

Figure 17

Other ways attendees have engaged with the ESIL community:

- *Might apply for a post-doc with ESIL in the future*
- *I am collaborating with ESIL staff on other projects*

Leveraging Connections Made at the Summit

Participants were asked, *How have you maintained or built on the professional connections that you made at the summit, if at all? Please elaborate.* Table 9 describes common themes from their open-ended responses (total responses $N = 23$).

Table 9

Key Themes	Highlights
Sustained Collaboration	Respondents reported regular meetings, continued project development, and proposal submissions. Some groups even expanded to invite new collaborators, enhancing research scope and diversity.
Conference Meetups	Respondents reunited with some summit peers at national conferences, including those associated with the American Geophysical Union (AGU) and the Ecological Society of America (ESA).
Connections that Diminished	Several respondents noted that connections diminished over time due to busy schedules, academic commitments, lack of structured follow-up mechanisms, and challenges in maintaining momentum via Slack or professional platforms.
Cohort Building	Some respondents found that summit peers became part of their graduate cohort, enhancing everyday academic collaboration.
Desire for Stronger Engagement Tools	Some respondents expressed a preference for better digital infrastructure to support long-term engagement. Despite some drift, there was general appreciation for ESIL's role in facilitating initial connections.

Satisfaction and Continuing Usage of Computing Environments

Respondents were asked how satisfied they were with various computing environments. Overall, the most popular and most used were **Local/Personal Computers (84% Very Satisfied or Satisfied)** followed by **CyVerse/ESIL Cyberinfrastructure (56% Very Satisfied or Satisfied)** (Figure 18).

100% of respondents were continuing to use their **Local/Personal Computer** for EDS work since engaging with ESIL, **48%** were using the **CyVerse/ESIL Cyberinfrastructure**, **36%** were using the **University Cluster/HPC**, and **32%** were using a **Commercial Cloud (AWS/Azure/Google)** (Figure 19).

Figure 18

Figure 19

Respondents were additionally asked to elaborate on how they have continued to use these computing environments and/or why they have continued using them. Responses are summarized below (total responses $N = 10$).

- *I am fortunate that my university has a lot of resources for environmental data science. However, it means that I did not have as big of a need for Cyverse/the ESIIIL infrastructure because of that.*
- *Not sure how to address this question.*
- *Minimal use in accessing large datasets via streaming.*
- *No one I work with works in CyVerse, so I've stayed on my local laptop and github.*
- *I only used CyVerse for work with ESIIIL, and I use my personal computer the most. I occasionally use my university's cluster when it is appropriate or needed.*
- *I professionally support researchers on HPC platforms myself.*
- *Has enabled to use of Python notebooks and using a common computing environment with team members.*
- *for working group*
- *I use them in a current grant-funded research project.*
- *I am processing land cover data in GEE. The reason is that it is practical, despite the learning curve of Java.*

Future Engagement with ESIIIL

93% of respondents **agreed** that they would be interested in attending a future ESIIIL Innovation Summit, with 77% strongly agreeing (Figure 20).

Figure 20

ESIIIL Culture: Longitudinal Reflections

Participants were asked, *In what ways could ESIIIL better support an open and welcoming culture at the ESIIIL Innovation Summit or other ESIIIL events?* **Overall, while participants acknowledged the program's efforts in inclusivity,** they also offered constructive feedback and suggestions for future improvement. Table 10 describes common themes from their open-ended responses (total responses $N = 18$).

Table 10

Key Themes	Highlights
Strong Existing Culture	Many respondents already felt that the 2024 Summit was respectful and welcoming. Several praised the way diverse ideas and perspectives were handled. Graduate students in particular noted feeling respected alongside professionals, which helped build confidence and comfort.
Facilitated Dialogue & Group Dynamics	Some respondents suggested introducing moderators or facilitators in breakout groups to manage conflicts and ensure balanced participation. Relatedly, one respondent suggested letting participants propose their own topics on Day 1 to enhance ownership and engagement.
Broader Representation	In order to increase representation, respondents suggested actions such as travel grants, mentorship, and dedicated sessions, as well as multilingual communication options and culturally sensitive event formats.
Accessibility & Preparedness	Some respondents had some pre-summit suggestions, such as offering pre-summit technical training such as asynchronous tutorials, sample scripts, and basic expectation guides, and clarifying what qualifies as Environmental Data Science to help diverse applicants feel like they “belong”.
Outreach & Awareness	Respondents suggested expanding promotion and recruitment to a broader range of institutions and disciplines to diversify participation.
Sustained Community Building	Respondents suggested year-round engagement platforms, such as online forums, slack communities, or regional meetups to encourage ongoing dialogue, networking, and collaboration beyond the Summit.

Future Support

Participants were asked, *Please comment on how ESIL can further support your work in EDS*. Table 11 describes common themes from their open-ended responses (total responses $N = 19$).

Table 11

Key Themes	Highlights
Training & Educational Content	Respondents suggested making presentations and workshops available online for a broader reach, or offering ongoing webinar series on key technical topics.
Practical Skill Development	Respondents suggested creating tutorials such as for GitHub and code-sharing to enhance reproducibility and collaboration, and perhaps even tailor training to non-coders or experimental research, supporting participation regardless of technical background.
Collaborative Structures	Respondents encouraged including training for more diverse skill sets in working groups (e.g., beyond coding), including fostering more interdisciplinary teams where different roles & skills contribute meaningfully.
Improved Communication & Outreach	Respondents asked that ESIL ensure that people are on the email list or Slack to stay informed, and maintain and promote the mailing list and Slack channels for post-summit engagement and opportunities.
Support Indigenous and Community-Centered Science	Suggestions to better directly support Indigenous and community-centered science including funding opportunities, technical resources, and partnership-building across cultural and scientific domains.
Sustained Engagement and Events	Respondents noted the value of continuing to host events like the Summits, Hackathons, and Training series.

How Summit Participants Learned About ESIL

Respondents were asked how they learned about ESIL. The most popular selection was **Word of Mouth (63%)**, followed by **I attended an ESIL Innovation Summit (58%)**, and **I received an email from ESIL@colorado.edu (33%)** (Figure 21).

Figure 21

Respondents who selected 'Other' were asked to elaborate. Below are their exact responses (N = 2):

- *Prior commitment to Earth Data Science staff*
- *[I] work at Earth Lab / ESIL*

Participation in ESIL

Figure 22

71% of respondents have been involved for ESIL for just **one year**, **13%** have been involved for **two** or **three years** separately, and only **4%** have been involved for **4 years** (Figure 22).

Figure 23

71% of respondents had received funding from ESIL to attend the 2024 Summit, **25%** had not, and **4%** preferred not to answer (Figure 23).

Respondents who received funding were asked how important funding was for participation in the ESIL Summit. **88%** said it was **Very Important**, and **12%** said it was **Moderately Important** (Figure 24).

Figure 24

Miscellaneous Event Feedback

Participants were asked to share any additional feedback on the ESIIIL Innovation Summit in a free-response question. Responses are summarized below (total responses N = 8).

- *I really appreciate the mission of ESIIIL and also appreciate your interest in constant improvement of your programs.*
- *None at the moment.*
- *I unfortunately fell out of touch with everyone at the conference, but I really liked the organization. I'm hoping I can figure out a way to get on an email list so I can stay in touch. I didn't learn about the summit this year until applications were closed. Thank you for the work you're doing to support and connect the environmental data science community.*
- *I would like to say, thank you for providing this platform.*
- *I'm looking forward to the next ESIIIL Summit in September!*
- *Only that I loved the opportunity to attend and I want to continue being involved.*

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Appendix A: 2024 ESIIIL Innovation Summit Agenda

ESIIIL Innovation Summit - Agenda
Big Data for Environmental Resilience and Adaptation
May 13-16

SEEC Building, 4001 Discovery Drive
 University of Colorado Boulder
<https://cu-esiil.github.io/Innovation-Summit-2024/>

Day Zero: Monday, May 13		
Time	Event	Location
1:30 – 3:30 PM	Participant Optional Fun Activities	NEON Tour Explore Downtown Pearl St. Go on a Hike
3:00 – 5:00 PM	Early Registration	SEEC Atrium
3:00 – 4:00 PM	Technical Help Desk <i>If you have questions about accessing Cyverse or GitHub, you can consult with our team!</i>	SEEC Auditorium
4:00 – 6:00 PM	Social Mixer	SEEC Cafe
Day One: Tuesday, May 14		
Time	Event	Location
8:30 AM	Registration Coffee & Tea, Light Breakfast Available	SEEC Atrium
9:00 AM	Welcome, Opening Ceremony	SEEC Auditorium
	Intentional Innovation: Call to Action Jennifer Balch (ESIIIL Director) & Emily Wilson (CO-WY Engine)	
	Event Logistics and Planning Team Introductions	
	Positive Polarities Warmup	
	Navigating Mis-Communications: Conflict as a Resource	
	Creating a Shared Language What is “Resilience?”	
10:30 AM	Break	SEEC Atrium

	Science of Team Science: What makes Great Teams?	SEEC Auditorium
	Big Data for Resilience	
	Exploring Resilience with Data Handout	
	Q&A	
12:15 PM	Group Photo	SEEC Atrium
12:30 PM	Lunch	
1:30 PM	Provocateur 1: Kate Thibault on Leveraging NEON to Understand Ecosystem Resilience Across Scales	SEEC Auditorium
	Explore Topics in Resilience and Adaptation	
3:15 PM	Break: Grab-and-go Snacks - when you head out to your breakout spaces	SEEC Atrium
3:30 PM	Team Breakouts: Innovation Time	Rooms to be allocated: S124, S127, S221, S225, S240, S249, C315, C325, S372, Earth Lab Conf Rm, ESIL Conf Table
4:30 PM	Report Back	SEEC Auditorium
	Whole Group Reflection	
	Day 1 Feedback	
5:00 PM	Day 1 Close	Dinner Venue Recommendation: Sanitas Brewing
Day Two: Wednesday, May 15		
Time	Event	Location
8:30 AM	Coffee & Tea, Light Breakfast Available	SEEC Atrium
9:00 AM	Welcome Back	SEEC Auditorium
	Provocateur 2: Claire Monteleoni Title/topic TBD	
	Prepare for the Day	
9:50 AM	Team Breakouts: Innovation Time	Breakout Spaces with your Team
12:30 PM	Lunch	SEEC Atrium
1:30 PM	Working Through the Groan Zone: Tips and Tricks to Thrive in the Groan Zone	SEEC Auditorium

1:50 PM	Team Breakouts: Innovation Time	Breakout Spaces with your Team
3:00 PM	Break	SEEC Atrium
4:20 PM	Report Back	SEEC Auditorium
	Whole Group Reflection	
5:00 PM	Day 2 Close	6:00pm CO-WY Engine Happy Hour at the Hotel Boulderado
Day Three: Thursday, May 16		
Time	Event	Location
8:30 AM	Coffee & Tea, Light Breakfast Available	SEEC Atrium
9:00 AM	Welcome Back	SEEC Auditorium
9:15 AM	Final Team Breakout: Prepare for the Final Report Back	Breakout Spaces with your Team
9:45 AM	Final Break	SEEC Atrium
10:00 AM	Final Report Back using GitHub pages	SEEC Auditorium
	What's Next?	
	Final Reflection	
	Closing	
12:00 PM	Day 3 Close	

Appendix B: Evaluation Surveys

2024 ESIL Summit Pre-Survey

ESIL Innovation Summit participants were selected based on their ability to help build the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community of the future. **Understanding the thoughts and opinions of Innovation Summit participants is therefore crucial.** Please fill out the information below to the best of your ability.

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: *We define EDS broadly to include any work where large data sets are used to drive discovery, solutions, and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.*

Please provide your first and last name

How did you learn about the ESIL Innovation Summit? Select all that apply.

- I attended a past ESIL Innovation Summit.
- I participated in an ESIL Hackathon or Coding event.
- I received an email from ESIL@colorado.edu.
- LinkedIn
- Twitter/X
- ESIL's website
- Word of Mouth - I heard from others about it
- An online forum or Slack channel (e.g., ECOLOG, AISES). If so, which one:

- Other:

What would you like to get out of your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit? Please share **1 - 3 personal goals** you have for the Summit.

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					

What is your primary role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (EDS)? Please select one.

- Director/Program Manager
- Project/Field Manager
- Analyst
- Technician
- Researcher
- Educator (Lecturer/K-12/Informal/Teaching Faculty)
- Student
- Other _____
- Prefer not to answer

Which of the following best describes your current career stage?

- Student (I am an undergraduate student or a graduate student)
- Early Career (I am a post-doctoral fellow, or have 0 to 5 years of professional experience.)
- Mid-Career (I have 6 to 15 years of professional experience.)
- Senior (I have more than 15 years of professional experience.)
- Other. Please describe. _____
- Prefer not to answer

What best describes the organization in which you work?

- Academic (higher education)
- Government: Federal
- Government: State
- Government: Local
- Industry
- K-12 or Informal Education
- Non-profit: Research and Development (FFRDC/National Labs/etc)
- Non-profit: other
- Private for-profit
- Tribal Organization
- Self

Other: _____

Prefer not to answer

Are you affiliated with an academic institution?

Yes

No

Unsure

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = Yes

With which type of academic institution are you affiliated? Select all that apply.

Community College/ 2-yr College

Professional Program

American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AAPISI)

Hispanic Serving Institution (HSI)

Historically Black University (HBCU)

Tribal College or Tribal-Serving Institution (TCU)

Minority Serving Institution (MSI)

Primarily Undergraduate Serving

Undergraduate and Graduate Serving

Research Intensive (R1/R2/etc)

If none of the options fit, how would you describe the main organization you are affiliated with?

Prefer not to answer

Which of the following categories best describe your highest level of education?

Some high school

High school diploma or equivalent

Vocational training

Some college

Associate degree (e.g. AA, AE, AFA, AS, ASN)

Bachelor's degree (e.g. BA, BBA, BFA, BS)

Some graduate work

Master's degree (e.g. MA, MBA, MFA, MS, MSW)

Applied or professional graduate degree (e.g. MD, DDS, JD)

Doctoral degree (e.g. EdD, PhD)

Not listed, please specify: _____

I prefer not to answer

In what field and in what year did you receive your highest degree?

What are the main professional societies to which you belong? Please select up to 5 professional societies from the drop-down menu, or type in the organization's full name.

Professional Society #1

Professional Society #2

Professional Society #3

Professional Society #4

Professional Society #5

In which disciplinary field(s) of Environmental Data Science do you MAINLY work? Select all that apply.

- Environmental Science
- Computer/Data Science
- Chemistry/ Biochemistry
- Social Science
- Economics
- Geoscience (Geology, Geography)
- Biological science
- Engineering
- Math
- Artificial Intelligence/ Machine Learning
- Other. Please specify. _____
- Prefer not to answer
- I don't work in an EDS field.

Where do you live?

I live in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:)

I am outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?)

I prefer not to answer

Where is your place of work located?

Place of work is in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:)

Place of work within a Tribal Nation (If yes, list the Tribal Nation)

Place of work is outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?)

I prefer not to answer

2024 ESIL Summit Reflection Survey

Thank you for joining us for the ESIL Innovation Summit. The ESIL leadership team would like to learn about your experiences at the Summit in order to better understand its impacts on innovation and building a broader Environmental Data Science network. Your feedback will help us to continue to improve future Summits as we build the broader ESD community.

Please provide your first and last name.

What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply.

- Speaker or Presenter
- Facilitator or Breakout Group leader
- ESIL leadership team
- ESIL advisory board member
- Participant
- Technical helper or Mentor
- Strategic partner

In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply.

- Head in the Clouds: Navigating the Basics of Cloud Computing (April 24, 2024)
- Feet on the Ground: Collaborating with Other People Using Cloud Computing (May 1, 2024)
- Voices in Concert: Cultural Intelligence, the Art of Team Science, and Community Skills (May 6, 2024)
- I did not attend the pre-Summit activities

Display This Question:

If In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply. != I did not attend the pre-Summit activities

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following components of the Pre-Summit trainings and activities prepared you for the Summit? (Select N/A if you did not participate in a component)

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Cloud Computing basics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaborating with others on Cloud Computing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
CyVerse Discovery Environment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The Art of Team Science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cultural Intelligence	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Community Skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Facilitator training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Display This Question:

If In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply. != I did not attend the pre-Summit activities

In what ways could the pre-Summit sessions be improved?

Overall, how satisfied were you with the ESIIIL Innovation Summit?

- Very Satisfied
- Moderately Satisfied
- Neutral
- Moderately Dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied

What were the best parts of the ESIIIL Innovation Summit?

How could the ESIIIL Innovation Summit be improved?

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following parts of the ESIIIL Innovator Summit were effective?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Positive Polarities Icebreaker activity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Provocations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout group time	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Balance of participation (active/passive learning)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social Activities (e.g., informal social mixer)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Whole Group/Community Discussions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reflections and Reporting Back	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
The goals of sessions were clearly communicated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting was well-facilitated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online resources were useful	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Speakers and presenters were engaging	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The unconference format worked well	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were plenty of networking opportunities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food provided was good	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interactive communication through Slack was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The ESIL Innovation Summit followed an Unconference Format. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree that the following characteristics of this format were implemented successfully.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
The breakout group topics were relevant to attendees.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were opportunities for participants to directly influence what was happening each day at the Summit.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There was an emphasis on welcoming the contributions of every participant.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Facilitation of the Summit was inclusive and welcoming of all ideas regardless of background experience (i.e., no idea is too trivial)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The atmosphere of the Summit was relaxed, open, friendly and fun.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The atmosphere of the Summit was welcoming for newcomers and those new to EDS.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were adequate opportunities to network with people of shared interests in EDS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Participants learned about and/or applied useful skills or tools related to EDS.

There were opportunities for collaborative, transdisciplinary work and exchange of ideas.

The statements below focus on how the technical support and cyberinfrastructure was helpful for your success at the Summit. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with each statement.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I gained a broader understanding of data science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I gained a broader understanding of cyberinfrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I learned about new opportunities for the synthesis of data in my field	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I learned about a new technology or techniques that I can apply in my research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about the ESIIIL **Innovation Summit overall**, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Colleagues showed a general respect for one another	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Colleagues respected the expertise of others in the group	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The contributions of all group members were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disagreements were handled constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting code of conduct was consistently implemented	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about **your own experiences** during the meeting, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I felt respected by my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Others in my group respected my expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt my contributions were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I handled disagreements constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Breakout groups gathered a group of enthusiastic collaborators	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout group brainstorming was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups developed initial plans for projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups created an outline for a project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups developed a plan to collaborate beyond the Summit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Plans for the future breakout group collaboration seem feasible	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent are you motivated to continue to work and innovate on ideas related to EDS?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

Please provide any other feedback you have on the breakout groups.

Display This Question:
If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Facilitator or Breakout Group leader
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member

What impacts do you anticipate the ESIL Innovation Summit will have over the next 6 months?

Display This Question:
If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Facilitator or Breakout Group leader
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team
Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member

In which ways, if at all, do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit will lead to innovation?

Display This Question:

If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Facilitator or Breakout Group leader

Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team

Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member

In which ways, if at all, do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit will shape a decadal research agenda of EDS?

In which ways do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit advanced the field of Environmental Data Science?

Please describe up to three new things that you will take away from the ESIL Innovation Summit (e.g., skills, ideas, contacts, other resources, etc.).

How many new connections or research collaborations have you made during the Summit?

- 1 to 3
- 4 to 6
- 7 to 9
- 10 or more
- I did not make any new connections or research collaborations.

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit has shaped your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of an Environmental Data Science (EDS) professional after having participated in the ESIL Innovation Summit.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>				
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>				

Please share any other feedback you have about the ESIL Innovation Summit.

2024 ESIL Summit Longitudinal Survey

Thank you for joining us for the ESIL Innovation Summit in May, 2024. The ESIL leadership team would like to learn about your experiences over the past several months since the Summit took place in order to better understand the Summit's long-term impacts. Your feedback will help us to continue to improve future Summits as we build the broader Environmental Data Science community.

What is your full name?

I believe that the 2024 ESIL Innovation Summit was beneficial for me personally.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

I would be interested in attending a future ESIL Innovation Summit.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neither Agree nor Disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

In which ways, if at all, do you think the ESIIIL Innovation Summit has advanced the field of Environmental Data Science?

How have you applied concepts, skills, tools, or resources that you learned about at the 2024 Summit, if at all? Please elaborate.

Have you continued working on ideas that you generated at the Summit?

- Yes
- No
- Uncertain

Display This Question:

If Have you continued working on ideas that you generated at the Summit? = Yes

Please elaborate on how you have continued working on ideas generated at the Summit.

How have you maintained or built on the professional connections that you made at the Summit, if at all? Please elaborate.

How have you engaged with the ESIL community since the Summit ended? (Select all that apply)

- I receive communications through the ESIL network email listserv
- I applied for an ESIL Hackathon event
- I participated in a Hackathon event
- I participated in an ESIL Training Webinar
- I was part of a proposal for an ESIL Working group
- I am a member of an ESIL Working Group
- I attended an ESIL Working Group information session
- I continued working with professional connections I made at the Summit
- I applied to become an ESIL Post-doc
- I participated in ESIL Stars Education program(s) (e.g., short courses, training, or internship)
- I have created an account with Cyverse
- I have used ESIL data cubes or data libraries
- I have used ESIL cyberinfrastructure
- Other: _____
- None of these applies

Since engaging with ESII, which of the following computing environments have you used in your Environmental Data Science work? (Select all that apply)

- Local/Personal Computer (Laptop/Desktop)
- Cyverse/ ESII Infrastructure
- University Cluster/ HPC
- NSF ACCESS (Cloud/HPC/HTC)
- Commercial Cloud (AWS/Azure/Google)
- Other: _____

Overall, how satisfied were you with the ease of locating, downloading and using these computing environments?

	Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Very Dissatisfied	N/A
Local/Personal Computer (Laptop/Desktop)	<input type="radio"/>					
Cyverse/ ESII Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>					
University Cluster/ HPC	<input type="radio"/>					
NSF ACCESS (Cloud/HPC/HTC)	<input type="radio"/>					
Commercial Cloud (AWS/Azure/Google)	<input type="radio"/>					
Other: _____	<input type="radio"/>					

If applicable, please elaborate on how you have continued to use these computing environments and/or why you have continued using them.

In what ways could ESIL better support an open and welcoming culture at the ESIL Innovation Summit or other ESIL events?

Please comment on how ESIL can further support your work in Environmental Data Science

How did you learn about ESIL?

- I attended an ESIL Innovation Summit
- I participated in an ESIL Hackathon or Coding Event
- I received an email from ESIL@colorado.edu
- LinkedIn
- Twitter/X
- ESIL's website
- Word of Mouth – I heard from others about it
- An online forum or Slack channel (e.g., ECOLOG, AISES). If so, which one? _____
- Other: _____

How long have you been involved in ESIL?

- 1 year
- 2 years
- 3 years
- 4 years

Did you receive funding from ESIL to attend the Summit?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

If Yes: How important was funding for you to participate in the ESIL Innovation Summit?

- Very Important
- Moderately Important
- Neither Important nor Unimportant
- Low Importance
- Not at all Important

Is there anything else you would like to share?